

Paper for Reading Report

English Class

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Object;

Azanila Firsaty Ladya Paper Analysis for ***DELISA FIGURE'S RELIGIOUS VALUE IN THE MEMORY MOVIE OF DELISA PRAYER***

Background and Analysis

Religion is a phrase that means “belief in God”, belief in supernatural powers over humans”. Aspect belief, worship, experience and consequences, knowledge, and appreciation are all interrelated in expressing these values. The problem raised in this study is the formation of a moral message. The purpose of this research is to see how the moral message is communicated memorization Delisa prayer directed by Sony Gaokasak in 2011 became the focus of the investigation. This study focuses on cinematic sequences, given at each step of the film. This research uses the Social Construction Theory of Peter L. Berger and Thomas Luckman. In the research, the approach used observation techniques, as well as related literature studies. This also studied using the framing model of Zhongdang Pan and Gerald M. Kosicki, which identifies: syntactic, scriptural, thematic, and rhetorical. This method to identify to identify to identify identifies aliases each round which that which which that which that contains a moral message, then each act is defined using four framing elements to determine how the moral message should be framed in the film. The results of the study suggest that morality can be taught through the events depicted in the film, that problems should not damage one's morals, and how to live life amid religious and social difficulties.

Memorization Film Shalat Delisa which is adapted from Tere Liye's novel with the same title is a literary work that the researcher discusses the meaning of religiosity. Many religious values can be learned from this film, especially from Delisa's character. We can learn about religious ideals and become more obedient to our religion by watching this film. The conclusion is :

1. The message package in Delisa's Memorizing Prayer film is described as a religious drama film. The subtleties of character issues are represented successfully due to the well-structured storyline, and the setting of shooting in pictures with an advanced plot makes the message conveyed easy to grasp. Morality, which combines religious and social conventions, is the film's fundamental focus. The director's moral lessons are packaged in simple dialogues with the main character, a girl named Delisa, who overcomes the sadness of losing a loved one with her fortitude and optimism. The presentation is wrapped in a religious component in the simplicity that is characteristic of people's lives in general, so it deserves to be a family spectacle. The

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use of the language of this film can highlight the moral lessons to be conveyed, and the plot becomes simple. to be understood & accepted in society.

2. In the findings of the video analysis, Delisa's Shalat Memorizing frame shows a morally significant statement. The moral principles in this video are: praying is better than sleeping, not being jealous and alert, loving people, being honest without expecting anything in return, and praying fervently.

Article/Media/Literacy Resources based Questions:

- 1) Is it Available data or information to answer it,

Yes, there is data that is carried out in this journal by analyzing and obtaining information

- 2) Is the data or information is obtained through scientific methods, such as interviews, observations, questionnaires, documentation, participation, and evaluations/tests,

Yes, data atau informasi diperoleh melalui ilmiah, di beberapa bagian makalah penelitian, bagian kuantitatif konten diperoleh dari sumber sekunder dari situs web online

- 3) Does it meet the originality requirements, identified through previous research mapping (state of the arts),

Identified through previous research mapping, this paper qualifies for originality because it represents my own ideas and thoughts.

- 4) Does it make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science,

This paper does not make a significant theoretical contribution to the development of science. This paper only provides moral values that can be applied

- 5) Does it regard controversial and unique issues that are currently happening,

The issues that occur do not contain conflicts because the lessons taken or researched are moral messages that can be practiced

- 6) The problem requires an answer and an immediate solution, but the answer is not yet known to the general public, and

The formulation of the problem is found in every research that is expected for the reader community to understand the journal we are discussing

- 7) The problem is posed within the limits of the researcher's interest (field of study) and ability.

The purpose of this research is to add insight about anything

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8) What developments or shifts were taking place at the time the event occurred,

the incident happened so quickly by consuming a lot of property and even taking a very sad life victim where he was abandoned by his mother and two brothers

9) What are the benefits of this research for the development of science and society at large in the future?

in this study there are many benefits to religious teachings where we will learn to be sincere and grow up with bad conditions

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